

Human proximity suppresses fish recruitment by altering mangrove-associated odour cues

This R Markdown includes descriptions of all variables and the code used for the analysis of the following three datasets:

1. Paired-choice experiments
2. Patch reef experiment
3. Leaf chemistry analysis

Note: All microbiome sequences have been submitted to the NCBI SRA database under the BioProject ID PRJNA630764. Associated analyses were conducted in QIIME and are outlined in the Supplementary Materials.

See methods section of manuscript and Supplementary Materials for further information on all data collection and analysis procedures.

```
# Set working directory and read the accompanying data files.
# This .Rmd file must be saved in the same folder as the data files.
# Do not use setwd(), but rather choose "Sessions/Set Working Directory/To Files Pa
ne Location"
# from the RStudio drop down menu

PairedChoice<-read.csv('SciRep_Data_Choicetrials.csv', strip.white=TRUE, header=TRUE)
PatchReef<-read.csv('SciRep_Data_Patchreef.csv', strip.white=TRUE, header=TRUE)
LeafChem<-read.csv('SciRep_Data_LeafChem.csv', strip.white=TRUE, header=TRUE)

# This R Markdown was conducted using R version 3.6.3

# Please ensure the following packages are installed:
# Rmisc
# car
# FSA
# rcompanion
```

1. Paired-choice experiments

Description of data

A series of choice experiments to examine the responses of fishes to different olfactory cues.

The dataset (SciRep_Data_Choicetrials.csv) contains the following variables (L-R):

- Fish: replicate individual.
- Date: date of replicate.

- Location: test site (Fiji or Belize).
- Species: fish species (*C.viridis*, *D. reticulatus*, *T.bifaciatum* , *S. partitus*).
- Test: test ID.
- Tester: identity of tester (RMB).
- Cue1: identity of Cue 1.
- Cue2: identity of Cue 2.
- SideOfCue1: Side of flume containing Cue 1 at start of trial (Left or Right).
- Replicate: replicate number within each test.
- P1_LS: number of time points (out of 24) an individual was recorded on the left side of flume during period 1.
- P1_RS: number of time points (out of 24) an individual was recorded on the right side of flume during period 1.
- P2_LS: number of time points (out of 24) an individual was recorded on the left side of flume during period 2.
- P2_RS: number of time points (out of 24) an individual was recorded on the right side of flume during period 2. +Total: total number of time points across full replicate (48).
- Total_LS: number of time points (out of 48) an individual was recorded on the left side of flume over the entire replicate.
- Total_RS: number of time points (out of 48) an individual was recorded on the left side of flume over the entire replicate.
- Total_In_Cue1: number of time points (out of 48) an individual was recorded in Cue 1 water over the entire replicate.
- Total_In_Cue2: number of time points (out of 48) an individual was recorded in Cue 2 water over the entire replicate.
- %_In_Cue1: percent of total replicate time (based on time points) an individual spent in Cue 1 water.
- %_In_Cue2: percent of total replicate time (based on time points) an individual spent in Cue 2 water.

Analysis

Load required packages. Summarise data.

```
library(Rmisc)
```

```
## Loading required package: lattice
```

```
## Loading required package: plyr
```

```
summarySE(PairedChoice, measurevar=c("X._In_Cue1"),groupvars=c("Test"))
```

```
##      Test  N X._In_Cue1      sd      se      ci
## 1     a 10  65.41667  6.069937 1.919483  4.342171
## 2     b 10  52.08333  9.316950 2.946278  6.664944
## 3     c 20  35.52083 11.420392 2.553677  5.344908
## 4     d 10  70.41667 14.258959 4.509079 10.200245
## 5     e 10  52.08333 10.803020 3.416215  7.728015
## 6     f 10  31.04167 10.367942 3.278631  7.416779
## 7     g 10  32.08333 13.036333 4.122451  9.325631
## 8     h 10  37.50000 17.123372 5.414886 12.249323
## 9     i 10  33.12500 12.006059 3.796649  8.588617
## 10    j 10  32.29167 14.240345 4.503192 10.186929
## 11    k 15  63.61111 11.270557 2.910045  6.241427
## 12    l 15  50.55556  5.131376 1.324916  2.841661
## 13    m 15  36.94444  8.534283 2.203543  4.726129
## 14    n 15  59.44444  8.178118 2.111581  4.528891
## 15    o 15  62.77778 18.846752 4.866210 10.436983
## 16    p 15  54.30556 12.159720 3.139626  6.733829
## 17    q 15  61.52778 11.938444 3.082493  6.611290
## 18    r 15  50.13889 12.005772 3.099877  6.648575
## 19    s 15  37.63889 10.128963 2.615287  5.609233
## 20    t 15  60.41667 14.369176 3.710105  7.957384
## 21    u 15  70.97222 15.012120 3.876113  8.313435
## 22    v 15  56.80556 12.362003 3.191855  6.845849
```

Species: *Chromis viridis*

Test A: *C. viridis*, Fresh leaves vs. Seawater.

Subset data for analysis.

```
a <- subset(PairedChoice, Test=='a')
a.se <- summarySE(a, measurevar="X._In_Cue1")
a.se
```

```
##      .id  N X._In_Cue1      sd      se      ci
## 1 <NA> 10  65.41667  6.069937 1.919483  4.342171
```

Test for normality, paired-samples t-test does not assume equal variance.

```
Diff.a=a$X._In_Cue1-a$X._In_Cue2
shapiro.test(x=Diff.a)
```

```
##
## Shapiro-Wilk normality test
##
## data:  Diff.a
## W = 0.83144, p-value = 0.03482
```

Assumption not met. Test for difference using non-parametric Wilcoxon test.

```
wilcox.test(a$X._In_Cue1, a$X._In_Cue2, paired=TRUE)
```

```
## Warning in wilcox.test.default(a$X._In_Cue1, a$X._In_Cue2, paired = TRUE):  
## cannot compute exact p-value with ties
```

```
##  
## Wilcoxon signed rank test with continuity correction  
##  
## data: a$X._In_Cue1 and a$X._In_Cue2  
## V = 55, p-value = 0.005666  
## alternative hypothesis: true location shift is not equal to 0
```

Conclusion: There is a difference (i.e. *C. viridis* spent more time in odour of Fresh leaves vs. Seawater; Fig. 1c).

Test B: *C. viridis*, Fresh leaves vs. Old leaves.

Subset data for analysis.

```
b <- subset(PairedChoice, Test=='b')  
b.se <- summarySE(b, measurevar="X._In_Cue1")  
b.se
```

```
##      .id  N X._In_Cue1      sd      se      ci  
## 1 <NA> 10  52.08333 9.31695 2.946278 6.664944
```

Test for normality.

```
Diff.b=b$X._In_Cue1-b$X._In_Cue2  
shapiro.test(x=Diff.b)
```

```
##  
## Shapiro-Wilk normality test  
##  
## data: Diff.b  
## W = 0.80967, p-value = 0.019
```

Assumption not met. Test for difference using non-parametric Wilcoxon test.

```
wilcox.test(b$X._In_Cue1, b$X._In_Cue2, paired=TRUE)
```

```
## Warning in wilcox.test.default(b$X._In_Cue1, b$X._In_Cue2, paired = TRUE):  
## cannot compute exact p-value with ties
```

```
## Warning in wilcox.test.default(b$X._In_Cue1, b$X._In_Cue2, paired = TRUE):  
## cannot compute exact p-value with zeroes
```

```
##
## Wilcoxon signed rank test with continuity correction
##
## data: b$X._In_Cue1 and b$X._In_Cue2
## V = 20, p-value = 0.8295
## alternative hypothesis: true location shift is not equal to 0
```

Conclusion: There is no difference (i.e. *C. viridis* did not spend more time in either odour; Fig. 1c).

Test C: *C. viridis*, Fresh leaves vs. Decaying leaves.

Subset data for analysis.

```
c <- subset(PairedChoice,Test=='c')
c.se <- summarySE(c,measurevar="X._In_Cue1")
c.se
```

```
##      .id  N X._In_Cue1      sd      se      ci
## 1 <NA> 20  35.52083 11.42039 2.553677 5.344908
```

Test for normality.

```
Diff.c=c$X._In_Cue1-c$X._In_Cue2
shapiro.test(x=Diff.c)
```

```
##
## Shapiro-Wilk normality test
##
## data: Diff.c
## W = 0.93128, p-value = 0.1634
```

Data normal. Test for difference using paired-sample t-test

```
t.test(c$X._In_Cue1,
       c$X._In_Cue2,
       paired=TRUE,
       comf.level=.95)
```

```
##
## Paired t-test
##
## data: c$X._In_Cue1 and c$X._In_Cue2
## t = -5.6699, df = 19, p-value = 1.822e-05
## alternative hypothesis: true difference in means is not equal to 0
## 95 percent confidence interval:
## -39.64815 -18.26852
## sample estimates:
## mean of the differences
## -28.95833
```

Conclusion: There is a difference (i.e. *C. viridis* spent less time in odour of Fresh leaves vs. Decaying leaves; Fig. 1c).

Species: *Dascyllus reticulatus*

Test D: *D. reticulatus*, Fresh leaves vs. Seawater.

Subset data for analysis.

```
d <- subset(PairedChoice, Test=='d')
d.se <- summarySE(d, measurevar="X._In_Cue1")
d.se
```

```
##      .id  N X._In_Cue1      sd      se      ci
## 1 <NA> 10   70.41667 14.25896 4.509079 10.20024
```

Test for normality.

```
Diff.d=d$X._In_Cue1-d$X._In_Cue2
shapiro.test(x=Diff.d)
```

```
##
## Shapiro-Wilk normality test
##
## data: Diff.d
## W = 0.93582, p-value = 0.5075
```

Data normal. Test for difference using paired-sample t-test

```
t.test(d$X._In_Cue1,
       d$X._In_Cue2,
       paired=TRUE,
       comf.level=.95)
```

```
##
## Paired t-test
##
## data: d$X._In_Cue1 and d$X._In_Cue2
## t = 4.5279, df = 9, p-value = 0.00143
## alternative hypothesis: true difference in means is not equal to 0
## 95 percent confidence interval:
##  20.43284 61.23382
## sample estimates:
## mean of the differences
##                40.83333
```

Conclusion: There is a difference (i.e. *D. reticulatus* spent more time in odour of Fresh leaves vs. Seawater; Fig. 1d).

Test E: *D. reticulatus*, Fresh leaves vs. Old leaves.

Subset data for analysis.

```
e <- subset(PairedChoice, Test=='e')
e.se <- summarySE(e, measurevar="X._In_Cue1")
e.se
```

```
##      .id  N X._In_Cue1      sd      se      ci
## 1 <NA> 10   52.08333 10.80302 3.416215 7.728015
```

Test for normality.

```
Diff.e=e$X._In_Cue1-e$X._In_Cue2
shapiro.test(x=Diff.e)
```

```
##
## Shapiro-Wilk normality test
##
## data:  Diff.e
## W = 0.93669, p-value = 0.5168
```

Data normal. Test for difference using paired-sample t-test.

```
t.test(e$X._In_Cue1,
       e$X._In_Cue2,
       paired=TRUE,
       comf.level=.95)
```

```
##
## Paired t-test
##
## data:  e$X._In_Cue1 and e$X._In_Cue2
## t = 0.60984, df = 9, p-value = 0.5571
## alternative hypothesis: true difference in means is not equal to 0
## 95 percent confidence interval:
## -11.28936 19.62270
## sample estimates:
## mean of the differences
##                4.166667
```

Conclusion: There is no difference (i.e. *D. reticulatus* did not spend more time in either odour; Fig. 1d).

Test F: *D. reticulatus*, Fresh leaves vs. Decaying leaves.

Subset data for analysis.

```
f <- subset(PairedChoice,Test=='f')
f.se <- summarySE(f,measurevar="X._In_Cue1")
f.se
```

```
##      .id  N X._In_Cue1      sd      se      ci
## 1 <NA> 10  31.04167 10.36794 3.278631 7.416779
```

Test for normality.

```
Diff.f=f$X._In_Cue1-f$X._In_Cue2
shapiro.test(x=Diff.f)
```

```
##
## Shapiro-Wilk normality test
##
## data:  Diff.f
## W = 0.92583, p-value = 0.4082
```

Data normal. Test for difference using paired-sample t-test.

```
t.test(f$X._In_Cue1,
       f$X._In_Cue2,
       paired=TRUE,
       comf.level=.95)
```

```
##
## Paired t-test
##
## data:  f$X._In_Cue1 and f$X._In_Cue2
## t = -5.7824, df = 9, p-value = 0.0002653
## alternative hypothesis: true difference in means is not equal to 0
## 95 percent confidence interval:
## -52.75022 -23.08311
## sample estimates:
## mean of the differences
## -37.91667
```

Conclusion: There is a difference (i.e. *D. reticulatus* spent less time in odour of Fresh leaves vs. Decaying leaves; Fig. 1d).

Test G: *D. reticulatus*, Suva water vs. Nukulau water.

Subset data for analysis.

```
g <- subset(PairedChoice,Test=='g')
g.se <- summarySE(g,measurevar="X._In_Cue1")
g.se
```

```
##      .id  N X._In_Cue1      sd      se      ci
## 1 <NA> 10    32.08333 13.03633 4.122451 9.325631
```

Test for normality.

```
Diff.g=g$X._In_Cue1-g$X._In_Cue2
shapiro.test(x=Diff.g)
```

```
##
## Shapiro-Wilk normality test
##
## data: Diff.g
## W = 0.90197, p-value = 0.2303
```

Data normal. Test for difference using paired-sample t-test.

```
t.test(g$X._In_Cue1,
      g$X._In_Cue2,
      paired=TRUE,
      comf.level=.95)
```

```
##
## Paired t-test
##
## data: g$X._In_Cue1 and g$X._In_Cue2
## t = -4.3461, df = 9, p-value = 0.001861
## alternative hypothesis: true difference in means is not equal to 0
## 95 percent confidence interval:
## -54.48460 -17.18207
## sample estimates:
## mean of the differences
## -35.83333
```

Conclusion: There is a difference (i.e. *D. reticulatus* spent less time in Suva water vs. Nukulau water; Fig. 2c).

Test H: *D. reticulatus*, Suva leaves vs. Nukulau leaves.

Subset data for analysis.

```
h <- subset(PairedChoice,Test=='h')
h.se <- summarySE(h,measurevar="X._In_Cue1")
h.se
```

```
##      .id  N X._In_Cue1      sd      se      ci
## 1 <NA> 10    37.5 17.12337 5.414886 12.24932
```

Test for normality.

```
Diff.h=h$X._In_Cue1-h$X._In_Cue2
shapiro.test(x=Diff.h)
```

```
##
## Shapiro-Wilk normality test
##
## data: Diff.h
## W = 0.73716, p-value = 0.00249
```

Assumption not met. Test for difference using non-parametric Wilcoxon test.

```
wilcox.test(h$X._In_Cue1, h$X._In_Cue2, paired=TRUE)
```

```
## Warning in wilcox.test.default(h$X._In_Cue1, h$X._In_Cue2, paired = TRUE):
## cannot compute exact p-value with ties
```

```
## Warning in wilcox.test.default(h$X._In_Cue1, h$X._In_Cue2, paired = TRUE):
## cannot compute exact p-value with zeroes
```

```
##
## Wilcoxon signed rank test with continuity correction
##
## data: h$X._In_Cue1 and h$X._In_Cue2
## V = 9, p-value = 0.1225
## alternative hypothesis: true location shift is not equal to 0
```

Conclusion: There is no difference (i.e. *D. reticulatus* did not spend more time in either odour; Fig. 2c).

Test I: *D. reticulatus*, Korovou water vs. Namuka water.

Subset data for analysis.

```
i <- subset(PairedChoice, Test=='i')
i.se <- summarySE(i, measurevar="X._In_Cue1")
i.se
```

```
##      .id  N X._In_Cue1      sd      se      ci
## 1 <NA> 10      33.125 12.00606  3.796649  8.588617
```

Test for normality.

```
Diff.i=i$X._In_Cue1-i$X._In_Cue2
shapiro.test(x=Diff.i)
```

```
##  
## Shapiro-Wilk normality test  
##  
## data: Diff.i  
## W = 0.89786, p-value = 0.2075
```

Data normal. Test for difference using paired-sample t-test.

```
t.test(i$X._In_Cue1,  
       i$X._In_Cue2,  
       paired=TRUE,  
       comf.level=.95)
```

```
##  
## Paired t-test  
##  
## data: i$X._In_Cue1 and i$X._In_Cue2  
## t = -4.4447, df = 9, p-value = 0.001612  
## alternative hypothesis: true difference in means is not equal to 0  
## 95 percent confidence interval:  
## -50.92723 -16.57277  
## sample estimates:  
## mean of the differences  
## -33.75
```

Conclusion: There is a difference (i.e. *D. reticulatus* spent less time in Korovou water vs. Namuka water; Fig. 2c).

Test J: *D. reticulatus*, Korovou leaves vs. Namuka leaves.

Subset data for analysis.

```
j <- subset(PairedChoice,Test=='j')  
j.se <- summarySE(j,measurevar="X._In_Cue1")  
j.se
```

```
##   .id  N X._In_Cue1      sd      se      ci  
## 1 <NA> 10  32.29167 14.24034 4.503192 10.18693
```

Test for normality.

```
Diff.j=j$X._In_Cue1-j$X._In_Cue2  
shapiro.test(x=Diff.j)
```

```
##  
## Shapiro-Wilk normality test  
##  
## data: Diff.j  
## W = 0.92451, p-value = 0.3961
```

Data normal. Test for difference using paired-sample t-test.

```
t.test(j$X._In_Cue1,  
       j$X._In_Cue2,  
       paired=TRUE,  
       comf.level=.95)
```

```
##  
## Paired t-test  
##  
## data: j$X._In_Cue1 and j$X._In_Cue2  
## t = -3.9324, df = 9, p-value = 0.003445  
## alternative hypothesis: true difference in means is not equal to 0  
## 95 percent confidence interval:  
## -55.79052 -15.04281  
## sample estimates:  
## mean of the differences  
## -35.41667
```

Conclusion: There is a difference (i.e. *D. reticulatus* spent less time in odour of Korovou leaves vs. Namuka leaves; Fig. 2c).

Species: *Thalassoma bifasciatum*

Test K: *T. bifasciatum*, Fresh leaves vs. Seawater.

Subset data for analysis.

```
k <- subset(PairedChoice, Test=='k')  
k.se <- summarySE(k, measurevar="X._In_Cue1")  
k.se
```

```
##   .id  N X._In_Cue1      sd      se      ci  
## 1 <NA> 15  63.61111 11.27056 2.910045 6.241427
```

Test for normality.

```
Diff.k=k$X._In_Cue1-k$X._In_Cue2  
shapiro.test(x=Diff.k)
```

```
##  
## Shapiro-Wilk normality test  
##  
## data: Diff.k  
## W = 0.88376, p-value = 0.054
```

Data normal. Test for difference using paired-sample t-test

```
t.test(k$X._In_Cue1,
      k$X._In_Cue2,
      paired=TRUE,
      comf.level=.95)
```

```
##
## Paired t-test
##
## data: k$X._In_Cue1 and k$X._In_Cue2
## t = 4.6773, df = 14, p-value = 0.0003562
## alternative hypothesis: true difference in means is not equal to 0
## 95 percent confidence interval:
##  14.73937 39.70508
## sample estimates:
## mean of the differences
##                27.22222
```

Conclusion: There is a difference (i.e. *T. bifasciatum* spent more time in odour of Fresh leaves vs. Seawater; Fig. 1a).

Test L: *T. bifasciatum*, Fresh leaves vs. Old leaves.

Subset data for analysis.

```
l <- subset(PairedChoice,Test=='l')
l.se <- summarySE(l,measurevar="X._In_Cue1")
l.se
```

```
##   .id  N X._In_Cue1      sd      se      ci
## 1 <NA> 15  50.55556 5.131376 1.324916 2.841661
```

Test for normality.

```
Diff.l=l$X._In_Cue1-l$X._In_Cue2
shapiro.test(x=Diff.l)
```

```
##
## Shapiro-Wilk normality test
##
## data: Diff.l
## W = 0.89029, p-value = 0.06774
```

Data normal. Test for difference using paired-sample t-test

```
t.test(l$X._In_Cue1,
      l$X._In_Cue2,
      paired=TRUE,
      comf.level=.95)
```

```
##
## Paired t-test
##
## data: l$X._In_Cue1 and l$X._In_Cue2
## t = 0.41931, df = 14, p-value = 0.6813
## alternative hypothesis: true difference in means is not equal to 0
## 95 percent confidence interval:
## -4.572211 6.794434
## sample estimates:
## mean of the differences
## 1.111111
```

Conclusion: There is no difference (i.e. *T. bifasciatum* did not spend more time in either odour; Fig. 1a)

Test M: *T. bifasciatum*, Fresh leaves vs. Decaying leaves.

Subset data for analysis.

```
m <- subset(PairedChoice,Test=='m')
m.se <- summarySE(m,measurevar="X._In_Cue1")
m.se
```

```
##   .id  N X._In_Cue1      sd      se      ci
## 1 <NA> 15  36.94444 8.534283 2.203543 4.726129
```

Test for normality.

```
Diff.m=m$X._In_Cue1-m$X._In_Cue2
shapiro.test(x=Diff.m)
```

```
##
## Shapiro-Wilk normality test
##
## data: Diff.m
## W = 0.95041, p-value = 0.5309
```

Data normal. Test for difference using paired-sample t-test

```
t.test(m$X._In_Cue1,
       m$X._In_Cue2,
       paired=TRUE,
       comf.level=.95)
```

```
##
## Paired t-test
##
## data: m$X._In_Cue1 and m$X._In_Cue2
## t = -5.9248, df = 14, p-value = 3.705e-05
## alternative hypothesis: true difference in means is not equal to 0
## 95 percent confidence interval:
## -35.56337 -16.65885
## sample estimates:
## mean of the differences
## -26.11111
```

Conclusion: There is a difference (i.e. *T. bifasciatum* spent less time in odour of Fresh leaves vs. Decaying leaves; Fig. 1a).

Test N: *T. bifasciatum*, South Water Cay water vs. Twin Cays water.

Subset data for analysis.

```
n <- subset(PairedChoice,Test=='n')
n.se <- summarySE(n,measurevar="X._In_Cue1")
n.se
```

```
##      .id  N X._In_Cue1      sd      se      ci
## 1 <NA> 15  59.44444 8.178118 2.111581 4.528891
```

Test for normality.

```
Diff.n=n$X._In_Cue1-n$X._In_Cue2
shapiro.test(x=Diff.n)
```

```
##
## Shapiro-Wilk normality test
##
## data: Diff.n
## W = 0.96676, p-value = 0.8075
```

Data normal. Test for difference using paired-sample t-test.

```
t.test(n$X._In_Cue1,
       n$X._In_Cue2,
       paired=TRUE,
       comf.level=.95)
```

```
##
## Paired t-test
##
## data:  n$X._In_Cue1 and n$X._In_Cue2
## t = 4.4727, df = 14, p-value = 0.000526
## alternative hypothesis: true difference in means is not equal to 0
## 95 percent confidence interval:
##  9.831107 27.946670
## sample estimates:
## mean of the differences
##                18.88889
```

Conclusion: There is a difference (i.e. *T. bifasciatum* spent less time in South Water Cay water vs. Twin Cays water; Fig. 2a).

Test O: *T. bifasciatum*, South Water Cay leaves vs. Twin Cays leaves.

Subset data for analysis.

```
o <- subset(PairedChoice,Test=='o')
o.se <- summarySE(o,measurevar="X._In_Cue1")
o.se
```

```
##   .id  N X._In_Cue1      sd      se      ci
## 1 <NA> 15   62.77778 18.84675 4.86621 10.43698
```

Test for normality.

```
Diff.o=o$X._In_Cue1-o$X._In_Cue2
shapiro.test(x=Diff.o)
```

```
##
## Shapiro-Wilk normality test
##
## data:  Diff.o
## W = 0.92739, p-value = 0.2493
```

Data normal. Test for difference using paired-sample t-test.

```
t.test(o$X._In_Cue1,
      o$X._In_Cue2,
      paired=TRUE,
      comf.level=.95)
```

```
##
## Paired t-test
##
## data:  o$X._In_Cue1 and o$X._In_Cue2
## t = 2.6258, df = 14, p-value = 0.01995
## alternative hypothesis: true difference in means is not equal to 0
## 95 percent confidence interval:
##  4.681589 46.429522
## sample estimates:
## mean of the differences
##                25.55556
```

Conclusion: There is a difference (i.e. *T. bifasciatum* spent less time in odour of South Water Cay leaves vs. Twin Cays leaves; Fig. 2a).

Test P: *T. bifasciatum*, South Water Cay treated leaves vs. Twin Cays treated leaves.

Subset data for analysis.

```
p <- subset(PairedChoice, Test=='p')
p.se <- summarySE(p, measurevar="X._In_Cue1")
p.se
```

```
##   .id  N X._In_Cue1      sd      se      ci
## 1 <NA> 15   54.30556 12.15972 3.139626 6.733829
```

Test for normality.

```
Diff.p=p$X._In_Cue1-p$X._In_Cue2
shapiro.test(x=Diff.p)
```

```
##
## Shapiro-Wilk normality test
##
## data:  Diff.p
## W = 0.88296, p-value = 0.05253
```

Data normal. Test for difference using paired-sample t-test.

```
t.test(p$X._In_Cue1,
      p$X._In_Cue2,
      paired=TRUE,
      comf.level=.95)
```

```
##
## Paired t-test
##
## data: p$X._In_Cue1 and p$X._In_Cue2
## t = 1.3714, df = 14, p-value = 0.1918
## alternative hypothesis: true difference in means is not equal to 0
## 95 percent confidence interval:
## -4.856546 22.078768
## sample estimates:
## mean of the differences
##                8.611111
```

Conclusion: There is no difference (i.e. *T. bifasciatum* did not spend more time in either odour; Fig. 2a).

Species: *Stegastes partitus*

Test Q: *S. partitus*, Fresh leaves vs. Seawater.

Subset data for analysis.

```
q <- subset(PairedChoice, Test=='q')
q.se <- summarySE(q, measurevar="X._In_Cue1")
q.se
```

```
##   .id  N X._In_Cue1      sd      se      ci
## 1 <NA> 15   61.52778 11.93844 3.082493 6.61129
```

Test for normality.

```
Diff.q=q$X._In_Cue1-q$X._In_Cue2
shapiro.test(x=Diff.q)
```

```
##
## Shapiro-Wilk normality test
##
## data: Diff.q
## W = 0.87404, p-value = 0.0387
```

Assumption not met. Test for difference using non-parametric Wilcoxon test.

```
wilcox.test(q$X._In_Cue1, q$X._In_Cue2, paired=TRUE)
```

```
## Warning in wilcox.test.default(q$X._In_Cue1, q$X._In_Cue2, paired = TRUE):
## cannot compute exact p-value with ties
```

```
## Warning in wilcox.test.default(q$X._In_Cue1, q$X._In_Cue2, paired = TRUE):
## cannot compute exact p-value with zeroes
```

```
##
## Wilcoxon signed rank test with continuity correction
##
## data: q$X._In_Cue1 and q$X._In_Cue2
## V = 78, p-value = 0.002478
## alternative hypothesis: true location shift is not equal to 0
```

Conclusion: There is a difference (i.e. *S. partitus* spent more time in odour of Fresh leaves vs. Seawater; Fig. 1b).

Test R: *S. partitus*, Fresh leaves vs. Old leaves.

Subset data for analysis.

```
r <- subset(PairedChoice, Test=='r')
r.se <- summarySE(r, measurevar="X._In_Cue1")
r.se
```

```
##   .id  N X._In_Cue1      sd      se      ci
## 1 <NA> 15  50.13889 12.00577 3.099877 6.648575
```

Test for normality.

```
Diff.r=r$X._In_Cue1-r$X._In_Cue2
shapiro.test(x=Diff.r)
```

```
##
## Shapiro-Wilk normality test
##
## data: Diff.r
## W = 0.94154, p-value = 0.4022
```

Data normal. Test for difference using paired-sample t-test

```
t.test(r$X._In_Cue1,
       r$X._In_Cue2,
       paired=TRUE,
       comf.level=.95)
```

```
##
## Paired t-test
##
## data: r$X._In_Cue1 and r$X._In_Cue2
## t = 0.044805, df = 14, p-value = 0.9649
## alternative hypothesis: true difference in means is not equal to 0
## 95 percent confidence interval:
## -13.01937 13.57493
## sample estimates:
## mean of the differences
## 0.277778
```

Conclusion: There is no difference (i.e. *S. partitus* did not spend more time in either odour; Fig. 1b).

Test S: *S. partitus*, Fresh leaves vs. Decaying leaves.

Subset data for analysis.

```
s <- subset(PairedChoice,Test=='s')
s.se <- summarySE(s,measurevar="X._In_Cue1")
s.se
```

```
##      .id  N X._In_Cue1      sd      se      ci
## 1 <NA> 15  37.63889 10.12896 2.615287 5.609233
```

Test for normality.

```
Diff.s=s$X._In_Cue1-s$X._In_Cue2
shapiro.test(x=Diff.s)
```

```
##
## Shapiro-Wilk normality test
##
## data: Diff.s
## W = 0.94638, p-value = 0.4693
```

Data normal. Test for difference using paired-sample t-test

```
t.test(s$X._In_Cue1,
      s$X._In_Cue2,
      paired=TRUE,
      comf.level=.95)
```

```
##
## Paired t-test
##
## data:  s$X._In_Cue1 and s$X._In_Cue2
## t = -4.7265, df = 14, p-value = 0.0003245
## alternative hypothesis: true difference in means is not equal to 0
## 95 percent confidence interval:
## -35.94069 -13.50376
## sample estimates:
## mean of the differences
## -24.72222
```

Conclusion: There is a difference (i.e. *S. partitus* spent less time in odour of Fresh leaves vs. Decaying leaves; Fig. 1b).

Test T: *S. partitus*, South Water Cay water vs. Twin Cays water.

Subset data for analysis.

```
t <- subset(PairedChoice,Test=='t')
t.se <- summarySE(t,measurevar="X._In_Cue1")
t.se
```

```
##      .id  N X._In_Cue1      sd      se      ci
## 1 <NA> 15   60.41667 14.36918 3.710105 7.957384
```

Test for normality.

```
Diff.t=t$X._In_Cue1-t$X._In_Cue2
shapiro.test(x=Diff.t)
```

```
##
## Shapiro-Wilk normality test
##
## data:  Diff.t
## W = 0.82424, p-value = 0.007655
```

Assumption not met. Test for difference using non-parametric Wilcoxon test.

```
wilcox.test(t$X._In_Cue1, t$X._In_Cue2, paired=TRUE)
```

```
## Warning in wilcox.test.default(t$X._In_Cue1, t$X._In_Cue2, paired = TRUE):
## cannot compute exact p-value with ties
```

```
## Warning in wilcox.test.default(t$X._In_Cue1, t$X._In_Cue2, paired = TRUE):
## cannot compute exact p-value with zeroes
```

```
##
## Wilcoxon signed rank test with continuity correction
##
## data: t$X._In_Cue1 and t$X._In_Cue2
## V = 63.5, p-value = 0.00729
## alternative hypothesis: true location shift is not equal to 0
```

Conclusion: There is a difference (i.e. *S. partitus* spent less time in South Water Cay water vs. Twin Cays water; Fig. 2b).

Test U: *S. partitus*, South Water Cay leaves vs. Twin Cays leaves.

Subset data for analysis.

```
u <- subset(PairedChoice, Test=='u')
u.se <- summarySE(u, measurevar="X._In_Cue1")
u.se
```

```
##      .id  N X._In_Cue1      sd      se      ci
## 1 <NA> 15   70.97222 15.01212 3.876113 8.313435
```

Test for normality.

```
Diff.u = u$X._In_Cue1 - u$X._In_Cue2
shapiro.test(x = Diff.u)
```

```
##
## Shapiro-Wilk normality test
##
## data: Diff.u
## W = 0.93914, p-value = 0.3717
```

Data normal. Test for difference using paired-sample t-test.

```
t.test(u$X._In_Cue1,
       u$X._In_Cue2,
       paired=TRUE,
       comf.level=.95)
```

```
##
## Paired t-test
##
## data: u$X._In_Cue1 and u$X._In_Cue2
## t = 5.4106, df = 14, p-value = 9.184e-05
## alternative hypothesis: true difference in means is not equal to 0
## 95 percent confidence interval:
## 25.31757 58.57131
## sample estimates:
## mean of the differences
## 41.94444
```

Conclusion: There is a difference (i.e. *S. partitus* spent less time in odour of South Water Cay leaves vs. Twin Cays leaves; Fig. 2b).

Test V: *S. partitus*, South Water Cay treated leaves vs. Twin Cays treated leaves.

Subset data for analysis.

```
v <- subset(PairedChoice, Test=='v')
v.se <- summarySE(v, measurevar="X._In_Cue1")
v.se
```

```
## .id N X._In_Cue1 sd se ci
## 1 <NA> 15 56.80556 12.362 3.191855 6.845849
```

Test for normality.

```
Diff.v=v$X._In_Cue1-v$X._In_Cue2
shapiro.test(x=Diff.v)
```

```
##
## Shapiro-Wilk normality test
##
## data: Diff.v
## W = 0.80019, p-value = 0.003697
```

Assumption not met. Test for difference using non-parametric Wilcoxon test.

```
wilcox.test(v$X._In_Cue1, v$X._In_Cue2, paired=TRUE)
```

```
## Warning in wilcox.test.default(v$X._In_Cue1, v$X._In_Cue2, paired = TRUE):
## cannot compute exact p-value with ties
```

```
## Warning in wilcox.test.default(v$X._In_Cue1, v$X._In_Cue2, paired = TRUE):
## cannot compute exact p-value with zeroes
```

```
##  
## Wilcoxon signed rank test with continuity correction  
##  
## data: v$X._In_Cue1 and v$X._In_Cue2  
## V = 65, p-value = 0.0438  
## alternative hypothesis: true location shift is not equal to 0
```

Conclusion: There is no difference (i.e. *S. partitus* did not spend more time in either odour; Fig. 2b).

2. Patch reef experiment

Description of data

A field-based experiment to examine settlement to patch reefs paired with mangrove leaves.

The dataset (SciRep_Data_Patchreef.csv) contains the following variables (L-R):

- Date: date of trial.
- Group: group that patch reef was part of (1-3) by date. Patch reefs were arranged in groups of 5, with 3 conducted each night.
- Replicate: treatment replicate (1-18).
- Location: Belize.
- Treatment: patch reef treatment (LD = developed site leaves, TLD = treated developed site leaves, LU = undeveloped site leaves, TLU = treated undeveloped site leaves, EC = empty control).
- Total_Recruitment: total number of recruits on patch reef replicate.
- Total_Species: total number of recruit species on patch reef replicate.
- T.bifasciatum: number of *Thalassoma bifasciatum* on patch reef replicate.
- S.leucostictus: number of *Stegastes leucostictus* on patch reef replicate.
- G.moringa: number of *Gymnothorax moringa* on patch reef replicate.
- H.bivittatus: number of *Halichoeres bivittatus* on patch reef replicate.
- S.adustus: number of *Stegastes adustus* on patch reef replicate.
- S.partitus: number of *Stegastes partitus* on patch reef replicate.
- C.rostrata: number of *Canthigaster rostrata* on patch reef replicate.
- P.arquatus: number of *Pomacanthus arcuatus* on patch reef replicate.
- Scarrus sp.: number of *Scarrus* sp. on patch reef replicate.
- Expected_settlement: expected settlement on patch reef replicate calculated by dividing total settlement for all patch reefs in the group by five.
- Expected_species: expected species on patch reef replicate calculated by dividing total species for all patch reefs in the group by five.
- Residual_settlement: residual settlement for patch reef replicate calculated as actual minus expected settlement.
- Residual_species: residual species for patch reef replicate calculated as actual minus expected species.

Analysis

Load required packages.

```
library(car)
```

```
## Loading required package: carData
```

```
library(FSA)
```

```
## ## FSA v0.8.30. See citation('FSA') if used in publication.  
## ## Run fishR() for related website and fishR('IFAR') for related book.
```

```
##  
## Attaching package: 'FSA'
```

```
## The following object is masked from 'package:car':  
##  
## bootCase
```

```
library(rcompanion)
```

Test A: effect of treatment on total settlement to patch reefs.

Check assumptions for parametric analysis.

```
shapiro.test(PatchReef$Residual_settlement)
```

```
##  
## Shapiro-Wilk normality test  
##  
## data: PatchReef$Residual_settlement  
## W = 0.96166, p-value = 0.009431
```

```
leveneTest(Residual_settlement ~ Treatment, data = PatchReef)
```

```
## Levene's Test for Homogeneity of Variance (center = median)  
##      Df F value Pr(>F)  
## group 4  3.7472 0.007411 **  
##      85  
## ---  
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
```

Assumptions not met. Test for difference using non-parametric Kruskal-Wallis rank sum test.

```
kruskal.test(Residual_settlement ~ Treatment, data = PatchReef)
```

```
##
## Kruskal-Wallis rank sum test
##
## data: Residual_settlement by Treatment
## Kruskal-Wallis chi-squared = 21.592, df = 4, p-value = 0.0002416
```

Significant difference identified. Use Dunn's tests of multiple comparisons for post hoc analysis.

```
dunnTest(PatchReef$Residual_settlement ~ PatchReef$Treatment, data = PatchReef, method = "bh")
```

```
## Dunn (1964) Kruskal-Wallis multiple comparison
```

```
## p-values adjusted with the Benjamini-Hochberg method.
```

```
## Comparison      Z      P.unadj      P.adj
## 1 EC - LD  2.9284971 3.406050e-03 1.703025e-02
## 2 EC - LU -1.6226754 1.046588e-01 1.495126e-01
## 3 LD - LU -4.5511725 5.334779e-06 5.334779e-05
## 4 EC - TLD  0.8801494 3.787784e-01 4.734730e-01
## 5 LD - TLD -2.0483477 4.052594e-02 6.754324e-02
## 6 LU - TLD  2.5028248 1.232065e-02 4.106884e-02
## 7 EC - TLU  0.4544771 6.494854e-01 7.216505e-01
## 8 LD - TLU -2.4740199 1.336022e-02 3.340056e-02
## 9 LU - TLU  2.0771526 3.778748e-02 7.557496e-02
## 10 TLD - TLU -0.4256723 6.703467e-01 6.703467e-01
```

Results of post hoc analysis summarised in Table S2.

Test B: effect of treatment on species settlement to patch reefs.

Check assumptions for parametric analysis.

```
shapiro.test(PatchReef$Residual_species)
```

```
##
## Shapiro-Wilk normality test
##
## data: PatchReef$Residual_species
## W = 0.97593, p-value = 0.09312
```

```
leveneTest(Residual_species ~ Treatment, data = PatchReef)
```

```
## Levene's Test for Homogeneity of Variance (center = median)
##      Df F value Pr(>F)
## group 4  0.7259 0.5767
##      85
```

Assumptions met. Test for difference using parametric one-way ANOVA.

```
rsp.aov <- aov(Residual_species ~ Treatment, data = PatchReef)
summary (rsp.aov)
```

```
##              Df Sum Sq Mean Sq F value    Pr(>F)
## Treatment      4  5.711  1.4278    6.494 0.000131 ***
## Residuals     85 18.689  0.2199
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
```

Significant difference identified. Use Tukey HSD test for post hoc analysis.

```
TukeyHSD(rsp.aov)
```

```
## Tukey multiple comparisons of means
## 95% family-wise confidence level
##
## Fit: aov(formula = Residual_species ~ Treatment, data = PatchReef)
##
## $Treatment
##              diff              lwr              upr              p adj
## LD-EC   -2.777778e-01 -0.71341906  0.15786350  0.3935347
## LU-EC    5.000000e-01  0.06435872  0.93564128  0.0161897
## TLD-EC   7.216450e-16 -0.43564128  0.43564128  1.0000000
## TLU-EC   1.111111e-01 -0.32453017  0.54675239  0.9534807
## LU-LD    7.777778e-01  0.34213650  1.21341906  0.0000325
## TLD-LD   2.777778e-01 -0.15786350  0.71341906  0.3935347
## TLU-LD   3.888889e-01 -0.04675239  0.82453017  0.1030014
## TLD-LU  -5.000000e-01 -0.93564128 -0.06435872  0.0161897
## TLU-LU  -3.888889e-01 -0.82453017  0.04675239  0.1030014
## TLU-TLD  1.111111e-01 -0.32453017  0.54675239  0.9534807
```

Results of post hoc analysis summarised in Table S3.

3. Leaf chemistry analysis

Description of data

Chemical analysis and comparison of leaves from South Water Cay vs. Twin Cays.

The dataset (SciRep_Data_LeafChem.csv) contains the following variables (L-R):

- Site: site of leaf collection (Southwater or Twin_cays).
- Sample: replicate number per site (1-15).
- Cu: concentration of copper ($\mu\text{g/g}$) in sample.
- As: concentration of arsenic ($\mu\text{g/g}$) in sample.
- Ti: concentration of titanium ($\mu\text{g/g}$) in sample.
- Mn: concentration of manganese ($\mu\text{g/g}$) in sample.

- Fe: concentration of iron ($\mu\text{g/g}$) in sample.
- Zn: concentration of zinc ($\mu\text{g/g}$) in sample.
- Rb: concentration of rubidium ($\mu\text{g/g}$) in sample.
- Sr: concentration of strontium ($\mu\text{g/g}$) in sample.
- Ba: concentration of barium ($\mu\text{g/g}$) in sample.
- NH₄N: concentration of ammonium-N ($\mu\text{g/g}$) in sample.
- PO₄P: concentration of phosphate-P ($\mu\text{g/g}$) in sample.

Analysis

Test A: comparison of copper (CU) concentrations in leaves from South Water Cay vs. Twin Cays.

Summarise data.

```
summarySE(LeafChem, measurevar=c("Cu"),groupvars=c("Site"))
```

```
##           Site N      Cu      sd      se      ci
## 1 Southwater 15 4.543631 2.692146 0.6951092 1.4908610
## 2 Twin_Cays 15 0.967141 1.033757 0.2669148 0.5724753
```

Check assumptions for parametric analysis.

```
a <- with(LeafChem, Cu[Site == "Southwater"] - Cu[Site == "Twin_Cays"])
shapiro.test(a)
```

```
##
## Shapiro-Wilk normality test
##
## data:  a
## W = 0.93798, p-value = 0.3577
```

```
leveneTest(Cu ~ Site, data = LeafChem)
```

```
## Levene's Test for Homogeneity of Variance (center = median)
##      Df F value Pr(>F)
## group 1  3.2213 0.08349 .
##      28
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
```

Assumptions met. Test for difference using parametric two-samples t-test.

```
t.test(Cu~Site, data = LeafChem, var.equal = TRUE)
```

```
##
## Two Sample t-test
##
## data: Cu by Site
## t = 4.8033, df = 28, p-value = 4.749e-05
## alternative hypothesis: true difference in means is not equal to 0
## 95 percent confidence interval:
## 2.051258 5.101721
## sample estimates:
## mean in group Southwater mean in group Twin_Cays
## 4.543631 0.967141
```

Conclusion: There is a difference in Cu concentration in leaves from each site.

Test B: comparison of arsenic (As) concentrations in leaves from South Water Cay vs. Twin Cays.

Summarise data.

```
summarySE(LeafChem, measurevar=c("As"),groupvars=c("Site"))
```

```
##           Site N           As           sd           se           ci
## 1 Southwater 15 0.08045347 0.02201135 0.005683307 0.01218948
## 2 Twin_Cays 15 0.02254623 0.02492013 0.006434350 0.01380031
```

Check assumptions for parametric analysis.

```
b <- with(LeafChem, As[Site == "Southwater"] - As[Site == "Twin_Cays"])
shapiro.test(b)
```

```
##
## Shapiro-Wilk normality test
##
## data: b
## W = 0.94686, p-value = 0.4764
```

```
leveneTest(As ~ Site, data = LeafChem)
```

```
## Levene's Test for Homogeneity of Variance (center = median)
##           Df F value Pr(>F)
## group 1 1.5653 0.2212
##           28
```

Assumptions met. Test for difference using parametric two-samples t-test.

```
t.test(As~Site, data = LeafChem, var.equal = TRUE)
```

```
##
## Two Sample t-test
##
## data: As by Site
## t = 6.7452, df = 28, p-value = 2.526e-07
## alternative hypothesis: true difference in means is not equal to 0
## 95 percent confidence interval:
## 0.04032183 0.07549265
## sample estimates:
## mean in group Southwater mean in group Twin_Cays
## 0.08045347 0.02254623
```

Conclusion: There is a difference in Cu concentration in leaves from each site.

Test C: comparison of titanium (Ti) concentrations in leaves from South Water Cay vs. Twin Cays.

Summarise data.

```
summarySE(LeafChem, measurevar=c("Ti"),groupvars=c("Site"))
```

```
##           Site N      Ti      sd      se      ci
## 1 Southwater 15 0.9281009 0.2494237 0.06440093 0.13812625
## 2 Twin_Cays 15 0.3987452 0.1440707 0.03719890 0.07978372
```

Check assumptions for parametric analysis.

```
c <- with(LeafChem, Ti[Site == "Southwater"] - As[Site == "Twin_Cays"])
shapiro.test(c)
```

```
##
## Shapiro-Wilk normality test
##
## data: c
## W = 0.8897, p-value = 0.06636
```

```
leveneTest(Ti ~ Site, data = LeafChem)
```

```
## Levene's Test for Homogeneity of Variance (center = median)
##           Df F value Pr(>F)
## group 1 1.5067 0.2299
##           28
```

Assumptions met. Test for difference using parametric two-samples t-test.

```
t.test(Ti~Site, data = LeafChem, var.equal = TRUE)
```

```
##
## Two Sample t-test
##
## data: Ti by Site
## t = 7.1176, df = 28, p-value = 9.592e-08
## alternative hypothesis: true difference in means is not equal to 0
## 95 percent confidence interval:
## 0.3770110 0.6817004
## sample estimates:
## mean in group Southwater mean in group Twin_Cays
## 0.9281009 0.3987452
```

Conclusion: There is a difference in Ti concentration in leaves from each site.

Test D: comparison of manganese (Mn) concentrations in leaves from South water Cay vs. Twin Cays.

Summarise data.

```
summarySE(LeafChem, measurevar=c("Mn"),groupvars=c("Site"))
```

```
##           Site N      Mn      sd      se      ci
## 1 Southwater 15 3.130211 2.790150 0.7204137 1.545134
## 2 Twin_Cays 15 2.379093 2.585643 0.6676102 1.431882
```

Check assumptions for parametric analysis.

```
d <- with(LeafChem, Mn[Site == "Southwater"] - Mn[Site == "Twin_Cays"])
shapiro.test(d)
```

```
##
## Shapiro-Wilk normality test
##
## data: d
## W = 0.94737, p-value = 0.484
```

```
leveneTest(Mn ~ Site, data = LeafChem)
```

```
## Levene's Test for Homogeneity of Variance (center = median)
##           Df F value Pr(>F)
## group 1 0.0533 0.8191
##           28
```

Assumptions met. Test for difference using parametric two-samples t-test.

```
t.test(Mn~Site, data = LeafChem, var.equal = TRUE)
```

```
##
## Two Sample t-test
##
## data: Mn by Site
## t = 0.76474, df = 28, p-value = 0.4508
## alternative hypothesis: true difference in means is not equal to 0
## 95 percent confidence interval:
## -1.260809 2.763046
## sample estimates:
## mean in group Southwater mean in group Twin_Cays
## 3.130211 2.379093
```

Conclusion: There is no difference in Mn concentration in leaves from each site.

Test E: comparison of iron (Fe) concentrations in leaves from South Water Cay vs. Twin Cays.

Summarise data.

```
summarySE(LeafChem, measurevar=c("Fe"),groupvars=c("Site"))
```

```
##      Site N      Fe      sd      se      ci
## 1 Southwater 15 62.78412 13.205424 3.409626 7.312920
## 2 Twin_Cays 15 23.11715 9.297976 2.400727 5.149048
```

Check assumptions for parametric analysis.

```
e <- with(LeafChem, Fe[Site == "Southwater"] - Fe[Site == "Twin_Cays"])
shapiro.test(e)
```

```
##
## Shapiro-Wilk normality test
##
## data: e
## W = 0.95792, p-value = 0.6562
```

```
leveneTest(Fe ~ Site, data = LeafChem)
```

```
## Levene's Test for Homogeneity of Variance (center = median)
##      Df F value Pr(>F)
## group 1 1.7542 0.1961
##      28
```

Assumptions met. Test for difference using parametric two-samples t-test.

```
t.test(Fe~Site, data = LeafChem, var.equal = TRUE)
```

```
##
## Two Sample t-test
##
## data: Fe by Site
## t = 9.5124, df = 28, p-value = 2.868e-10
## alternative hypothesis: true difference in means is not equal to 0
## 95 percent confidence interval:
## 31.12507 48.20886
## sample estimates:
## mean in group Southwater mean in group Twin_Cays
##                62.78412                23.11715
```

Conclusion: There is a difference in Fe concentration in leaves from each site.

Test F: comparison of zinc (Zn) concentrations in leaves from South Water Cay vs. Twin Cays.

Summarise data.

```
summarySE(LeafChem, measurevar=c("Zn"),groupvars=c("Site"))
```

```
##           Site N      Zn      sd      se      ci
## 1 Southwater 15 2.6980346 1.8935107 0.4889023 1.0485912
## 2 Twin_Cays 15 0.4646234 0.4481133 0.1157023 0.2481569
```

Check assumptions for parametric analysis.

```
f <- with(LeafChem, Zn[Site == "Southwater"] - Zn[Site == "Twin_Cays"])
shapiro.test(f)
```

```
##
## Shapiro-Wilk normality test
##
## data: f
## W = 0.92218, p-value = 0.208
```

```
leveneTest(Zn ~ Site, data = LeafChem)
```

```
## Levene's Test for Homogeneity of Variance (center = median)
##      Df F value Pr(>F)
## group 1 20.333 0.000106 ***
##      28
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
```

Assumptions not met. Test for difference using non-parametric Wilcoxon test.

```
wilcox.test(Zn~Site, data = LeafChem, paired=FALSE)
```

```
## Warning in wilcox.test.default(x = c(3.175941938, 3.863471525, 6.343287927, :  
## cannot compute exact p-value with ties
```

```
##  
## Wilcoxon rank sum test with continuity correction  
##  
## data: Zn by Site  
## W = 203, p-value = 0.0001879  
## alternative hypothesis: true location shift is not equal to 0
```

Conclusion: There is a difference in Zn concentration in leaves from each site.

Test G: comparison of rubidium (Rb) concentrations in leaves from South Water Cay vs. Twin Cays.

Summarise data.

```
summarySE(LeafChem, measurevar=c("Rb"),groupvars=c("Site"))
```

```
##      Site N      Rb      sd      se      ci  
## 1 Southwater 15 1.832266 0.4422091 0.11417789 0.2448872  
## 2 Twin_Cays 15 1.574631 0.2952497 0.07623316 0.1635039
```

Check assumptions for parametric analysis.

```
g <- with(LeafChem, Rb[Site == "Southwater"] - Rb[Site == "Twin_Cays"])  
shapiro.test(g)
```

```
##  
## Shapiro-Wilk normality test  
##  
## data: g  
## W = 0.97696, p-value = 0.9445
```

```
leveneTest(Rb ~ Site, data = LeafChem)
```

```
## Levene's Test for Homogeneity of Variance (center = median)  
##      Df F value Pr(>F)  
## group 1  2.8475 0.1026  
##      28
```

Assumptions met. Test for difference using parametric two-samples t-test.

```
t.test(Rb~Site, data = LeafChem, var.equal = TRUE)
```

```
##
## Two Sample t-test
##
## data: Rb by Site
## t = 1.8766, df = 28, p-value = 0.07103
## alternative hypothesis: true difference in means is not equal to 0
## 95 percent confidence interval:
## -0.0235871 0.5388577
## sample estimates:
## mean in group Southwater mean in group Twin_Cays
## 1.832266 1.574631
```

Conclusion: There is no difference in Rb concentration in leaves from each site.

Test H: comparison of strontium (Sr) concentrations in leaves from South Water Cay vs. Twin Cays.

Summarise data.

```
summarySE(LeafChem, measurevar=c("Sr"),groupvars=c("Site"))
```

```
##      Site N      Sr      sd      se      ci
## 1 Southwater 15 171.1559 31.89420 8.235047 17.66242
## 2 Twin_Cays 15 114.5076 20.48907 5.290254 11.34647
```

Check assumptions for parametric analysis.

```
h <- with(LeafChem, Sr[Site == "Southwater"] - Sr[Site == "Twin_Cays"])
shapiro.test(h)
```

```
##
## Shapiro-Wilk normality test
##
## data: h
## W = 0.9185, p-value = 0.1827
```

```
leveneTest(Sr ~ Site, data = LeafChem)
```

```
## Levene's Test for Homogeneity of Variance (center = median)
##      Df F value Pr(>F)
## group 1  1.9922 0.1691
##      28
```

Assumptions met. Test for difference using parametric two-samples t-test.

```
t.test(Sr~Site, data = LeafChem, var.equal = TRUE)
```

```
##
## Two Sample t-test
##
## data: Sr by Site
## t = 5.7876, df = 28, p-value = 3.246e-06
## alternative hypothesis: true difference in means is not equal to 0
## 95 percent confidence interval:
## 36.59874 76.69790
## sample estimates:
## mean in group Southwater mean in group Twin_Cays
## 171.1559 114.5076
```

Conclusion: There is a difference in Rb concentration in leaves from each site.

Test I: comparison of barium (Ba) concentrations in leaves from South Water Cay vs. Twin Cays.

Summarise data.

```
summarySE(LeafChem, measurevar=c("Ba"),groupvars=c("Site"))
```

```
##           Site N      Ba      sd      se      ci
## 1 Southwater 15 0.3500881 0.3312544 0.08552951 0.1834425
## 2 Twin_Cays 15 0.1160515 0.4494657 0.11605154 0.2489058
```

Check assumptions for parametric analysis.

```
i <- with(LeafChem, Ba[Site == "Southwater"] - Ba[Site == "Twin_Cays"])
shapiro.test(i)
```

```
##
## Shapiro-Wilk normality test
##
## data: i
## W = 0.8567, p-value = 0.02164
```

```
leveneTest(Ba ~ Site, data = LeafChem)
```

```
## Levene's Test for Homogeneity of Variance (center = median)
##           Df F value Pr(>F)
## group 1 2.2103 0.1483
##           28
```

Assumptions not met. Test for difference using non-parametric Wilcoxon test.

```
wilcox.test(Ba~Site, data = LeafChem, paired=FALSE)
```

```
## Warning in wilcox.test.default(x = c(0.422814695, 0.743559836, 0.551513687, :  
## cannot compute exact p-value with ties
```

```
##  
## Wilcoxon rank sum test with continuity correction  
##  
## data: Ba by Site  
## W = 168, p-value = 0.006554  
## alternative hypothesis: true location shift is not equal to 0
```

Conclusion: There is a difference in Ba concentration in leaves from each site.

Test J: comparison of ammonium-N (NH₄-N) concentrations in leaves from South Water Cay vs. Twin Cays.

Summarise data.

```
summarySE(LeafChem, measurevar=c("NH4N"),groupvars=c("Site"))
```

```
##      Site N    NH4N    sd    se    ci  
## 1 Southwater 15 594.4673 250.4478 64.66535 138.69338  
## 2 Twin_Cays 15 296.6593 168.5495 43.51930 93.33962
```

Check assumptions for parametric analysis.

```
j <- with(LeafChem, NH4N[Site == "Southwater"] - NH4N[Site == "Twin_Cays"])  
shapiro.test(j)
```

```
##  
## Shapiro-Wilk normality test  
##  
## data: j  
## W = 0.97193, p-value = 0.8855
```

```
leveneTest(NH4N ~ Site, data = LeafChem)
```

```
## Levene's Test for Homogeneity of Variance (center = median)  
##      Df F value Pr(>F)  
## group 1  1.9505 0.1735  
##      28
```

Assumptions met. Test for difference using parametric two-samples t-test.

```
t.test(NH4N~Site, data = LeafChem, var.equal = TRUE)
```

```
##
## Two Sample t-test
##
## data: NH4N by Site
## t = 3.8207, df = 28, p-value = 0.0006782
## alternative hypothesis: true difference in means is not equal to 0
## 95 percent confidence interval:
## 138.1434 457.4725
## sample estimates:
## mean in group Southwater mean in group Twin_Cays
##          594.4673          296.6593
```

Conclusion: There is a difference in NH4N concentration in leaves from each site.

Test K: comparison of phosphate-P (PO4-P) concentrations in leaves from South Water Cay vs. Twin Cays.

Summarise data.

```
summarySE(LeafChem, measurevar=c("P04P"),groupvars=c("Site"))
```

```
##           Site N    P04P      sd      se      ci
## 1 Southwater 15 1278.867 355.0698 91.67862 196.63109
## 2 Twin_Cays 15  911.367 177.4343 45.81333  98.25982
```

Check assumptions for parametric analysis.

```
k <- with(LeafChem, P04P[Site == "Southwater"] - NH4N[Site == "Twin_Cays"])
shapiro.test(k)
```

```
##
## Shapiro-Wilk normality test
##
## data: k
## W = 0.76479, p-value = 0.001345
```

```
leveneTest(P04P ~ Site, data = LeafChem)
```

```
## Levene's Test for Homogeneity of Variance (center = median)
##           Df F value Pr(>F)
## group 1  0.7036 0.4087
##           28
```

Assumptions not met. Test for difference using non-parametric Wilcoxon test.

```
wilcox.test(P04P~Site, data = LeafChem, paired=FALSE)
```

```
##  
## Wilcoxon rank sum test  
##  
## data: P04P by Site  
## W = 196, p-value = 0.0002643  
## alternative hypothesis: true location shift is not equal to 0
```

Conclusion: There is a difference in Ba concentration in leaves from each site.

End of R Markdown